

Invisible in Search? Auditing Gender Bias in the Visual Representation of Holocaust Victims on Google

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1. Introduction

Many studies (e.g., Kay et al., 2015; Otterbacher et al., 2017) indicate the risk of search engine algorithms reiterating or amplifying gender bias, particularly regarding the representation of vulnerable groups (e.g., women of colour and from countries outside of the Global North; e.g., Noble, 2018; Urman & Makhortykh, 2024). However, despite the growing number of areas in which gender bias is discussed in the context of web search, for instance, politics (Pradel, 2021) or innovation (Makhortykh et al., 2021), its role in some societally relevant areas remains understudied. One of such areas is heritage, particularly heritage dealing with mass atrocities such as the Holocaust, which until now is often contested and frequently instrumentalized for the needs of today's politics.

To address these questions, we conduct an algorithm audit of how Google, one of the world's most commonly used search engines, visually represents victims of the Holocaust and whether such representation is prone to gender bias. We are interested in gender bias in image search, both due to the strong affective potential that visual images have, and much research on the topic so far has focused on image search. Specifically, we manually collected the top 50 image search results from 50 locations worldwide (with most of the locations in Europe, where the Holocaust took place). We used a VPN to simulate local IP addresses for all the locations and also translated the gender-neutral query - i.e., "Holocaust victims" - into the official languages of the country corresponding to each location.

After collecting the data, we used computer vision to automatically identify the number of human beings present on each image appearing in search results and their sex (we recognize that sex is a simplified proxy for a complex gender construct, but automated identification of different forms of gender remains a challenging task). For this aim, we used Amazon Rekognition API, as earlier studies (e.g., Ulloa et al., 2024) demonstrated that its performance for analysing human-related features (including the number of individuals and their age) is on par with human-made assessments. To confirm it, we conducted a sanity test using a small subset of images, which were analyzed by the authors and then compared to the outcomes of the Rekognition API.

For the analysis, we are going to test three hypotheses, which are informed by research on Holocaust heritage, particularly the memorialization of victims. The first hypothesis is that image search results will contain more images of women than of men due to Holocaust-related memorial practices in many European countries focusing on images of more vulnerable victims, such as women and children. The second hypothesis is that the number of images with humans will be higher for countries from which more Holocaust victims originated and where we find more Holocaust memorial sites. The third hypothesis is that the present-day gender equality score will influence the distribution of female and

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male victims depicted in image search results. To test these hypotheses, we will use correlation analysis and generalized linear mixed effects models.

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